

Active Learning in Construction Management Capstone Projects: Bridging Theory and Practice

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Abstract

Construction engineering and management is a complex field that involves technical and managerial dimensions, such as project planning, structural design, construction processes, legal frameworks, and environmental sustainability. Each facet demands a nuanced understanding and proficiency in diverse skill sets. In response to this complexity, academic programs in construction engineering must evolve to incorporate innovative learning strategies that effectively prepare students for the dynamic challenges of the industry. Active learning methodologies emerge as a cornerstone in this endeavour, offering students hands-on experiences to deepen their understanding of technical concepts and develop crucial soft skills, including communication, teamwork, and leadership, which are indispensable for success in the construction industry. The School of Civil Engineering at Universidad Industrial de Santander in Colombia, has implemented capstone projects, supported by active learning strategies, to offer students the opportunity to apply theoretical knowledge to real-world scenarios using innovative methodologies such as Building Information Modelling (BIM) and sustainability features. By engaging in capstone projects, students not only develop practical skills but also gain valuable insights into emerging industry trends and challenges. This article presents our experiences in developing capstone projects and their role in bridging theoretical concepts with practical applications in a dynamic learning environment. The capstone projects have helped identify students' strengths and weaknesses, areas for improvement in our students' skillsets, as well as how they adopt innovative methodologies and address emerging issues. These insights have informed ongoing curriculum reforms aimed at ensuring alignment with industry demands and promoting educational excellence. Moving forward, we are committed to further enhancing our active learning strategies and leveraging emerging technologies to provide students with the comprehensive preparation needed to succeed in the dynamic field of construction engineering and management.

Keywords: Active Learning; Capstone Projects; Engineering Education; Learning Methodologies; Project Based Learning.

1 Introduction

Emerging technology, complex problems, collaborative environments, among other features, characterize the engineering practice and lead engineering students to acquire project-environment and problem-solving skills (Hassan et al., 2011). In fact, some authors argue that problem-solving skills, communication, and teamwork are essential for engineers to succeed in their careers (Passow & Passow, 2017). In this sense, accreditation processes, such as the Accreditation Board of Engineering and Technology (ABET), promote the development of engineering practice skills in accordance with the institutional mission, educational objectives, student outcomes, curricula, and assessment methods (Mejía-Aguilar et al., 2020).

Active learning is an innovative pedagogical approach that promotes student-near environment to implement hands-on projects, where they develop skills and competencies such as problem-solving, team collaboration, effective communication, and decision-making, among others (Xu et al., 2019, 2022). There has been an interest on the part of educational institutions, educators and industry in implementing the capstone-design or integrative project, as an active learning activity of corner design experience (Zheng et al., 2021). Design experiences encourage multidisciplinary collaboration and teamwork, in order to find solutions to real-world problems related to professional practice and ensure that students can perform effectively in a team, to work collaboratively as a team (Parker et al., 2019).

Because a excel professional performance of engineers is essential for achieving project success, the professional training of students must be guaranteed with the development of competencies and skills related to design and construction experiences. However, authors highlight some shortcomings that affect the professional performance of engineers are lack of collaborative work experience, assertive communication problems and absence of leadership when assuming assigned roles within a team work stand out (Dillon & Cheney, 2009). This situation is due to the fact that students focus only on completing their tasks no matter how it is done, which often limits the development of comprehensive knowledge and promotes the acquisition of fragmented and incomplete knowledge (Jones & Tadros, 2010).

Although it is important to implement capstone design type courses within project-based engineering programs, questions arise in practical life related to bridge theory and practice, the pedagogical approaches, methods and strategies, the development of skills and curricular issues. The answers to these questions and others related to capstone design would provide some guidance for implementing pedagogical and curricular strategies in engineering programs. Therefore, the purpose of this paper was to analyze and discuss experiences in developing capstone projects and their role in bridging theoretical concepts with practical applications in a dynamic learning environment. The capstone project was implemented at the School of Civil Engineering at Universidad Industrial de Santander in Colombia, supported by active learning strategies, to offer students the opportunity to apply theoretical knowledge to real-world scenarios using innovative methodologies such as Building Information Modelling (BIM) and sustainability features.

2 Active Learning and Capstone Design

Active learning plays a pivotal role in enhancing the capstone design experience for students in engineering education. By shifting the focus from passive reception to active engagement, active learning fosters deeper student involvement, critical skill development, and real-world application. This section explores various learning approaches and methods that leverage active learning principles to enrich the capstone design process.

2.1 Learning Approaches and Methods

Active learning approach enriches the capstone design experience by promoting student engagement, critical skill development, real-world application, and continuous learning and improvement. In capstone design projects, students are actively involved in solving real-world engineering problems, applying theoretical knowledge to practical scenarios, and collaborating with peers to develop innovative solutions.

Active learning is a student-centered learning approach that involve actively engaging students in the learning process through activities and experiences, rather than relying solely on traditional instructor-led lectures. This approach makes students active participants in their own learning. The emphasis of the active learning is more on learning and less on teaching, and it requires instructors to incorporate more active and student-centered learning methods into their courses. These methods include: Learning Factory (Lamancusa et al., 2008); Project-based learning (PBL) (Wang et al., 2012); Problem-Based Learning (Dunnigan et al., 2020); Experiential learning (Bailey & Debartolo, 2007); Collaborative learning (Xu et al., 2022); Flipped classroom (Lewin & Barzilai, 2017); Socratic Method (Golanbari & Garlikov, 2008); Enquiry-guided project learning approach (Khraisheh & Benyahia, 2012); and Hands-on, team-oriented learning (Building-as-lab concept) (Goldberg & Rank, 2013).

2.2 Skills Development

Capstone design projects combined with active learning methodologies facilitate the development of professional and design skills essential for engineers. Through active learning, students are encouraged to think critically, analyze problems from multiple perspectives, and collaborate effectively with their peers. These skills are invaluable in tackling complex engineering challenges encountered in capstone design projects and in professional practice. These professional skills include: Teamwork (Hanus & Russell, 2007); Diversity (Hanus & Russell, 2007); Leadership (Hanus & Russell, 2007; Lamancusa et al., 2008); Communications (Hanus & Russell, 2007); Problem-solving (Dunnigan et al., 2020); Critical thinking (Golanbari & Garlikov, 2008); Ethics (Santi, 2000); and Design thinking (Goldberg & Rank, 2013).

2.3 Curriculum and Administrative Issues

Active learning in capstone design projects emphasizes real-world relevance and application of engineering principles. By engaging in hands-on, project-based activities, students gain practical experience and learn to apply theoretical knowledge to solve authentic engineering problems. By integrating active learning throughout the curriculum and aligning it with the objectives of capstone design projects, educators can provide students with a rich and transformative learning experience. This learning approach sometimes generates curriculum and administrative issues such as:

- Striking a balance between theoretical concepts and practical skills.
- Managing the increased workload for professors.
- Coordinating logistics and scheduling for seamless project execution.

3 Methodology

This study is based on a qualitative analysis of Capstone Projects conducted in undergraduate construction management courses within the School of Civil Engineering at Universidad Industrial de Santander (UIS). These projects have been implemented across various courses, particularly focusing on project management courses. Although the civil engineering program at UIS emphasizes areas like structural design and water resources, there are few mandatory courses in project management. Therefore, managing these projects allows for the integration of various areas while fostering new knowledge among students.

The development process of the capstone project has evolved over several semesters, accumulating lessons learned along the way. Students are divided into groups of five or six students to develop the project. Starting from architectural and structural drawings of a building, students model the building using the Building Information Modeling (BIM) methodology and considering ISO 19650 specifications. Additionally, sustainability aspects not initially included in the drawings are addressed by approximating with the EDGE Green Building Certification application. The team also conducts an approach to site localization and market studies. Deliverables include finished models, sets of plans, quantity estimations, project scheduling for construction duration estimation, and project budgeting for cost estimation. Groups must demonstrate evidence of collaborative work and make oral presentations at partial submissions and a final presentation with posters. This showcases the development of soft skills such as teamwork and oral communication.

Given that the UIS civil engineering program lacks a BIM course, the project is overseen by a main course and a weekly BIM workshop. Attendance at the workshop is not mandatory, but classes are broadcasted live for student convenience, and recordings are available for consultation. The workshop schedule aligns with topics covered in the theoretical class. Table 1 presents a workshop schedule for the Construction course.

Table 1. BIM Workshop Schedule.

Week	Scope							Time (Schedule)				Cost (Budget)			
	W1	W2	W3	W4	W5	W6	W7	W8	W9	W10	W11	W12	W13	W14	W15
Topics	Course Introduction of project scope and schedule	Introduction to BIM software ISO 19650 standard presentation	Terrain modeling	Structure modeling (Foundation and superstructure)	Architecture modeling	Architecture modeling Stair modeling	Generation of Plans	Obtaining quantities from a BIM model	Reading hydraulic, sanitary, and electrical plans	Introduction to sustainability - EDGE app Energy and water consumption	Hydraulic and Electrical networks modeling	BIM coordination	Integrating times and costs with the model	Rendering and Poster	
Deliverables							Delivery 1				Delivery 2			Delivery 3	
Oral Presentation								Presentation 1				Presentation 2			Final Presentation

4 Results

The capstone project in the Construction management area has been developed over five consecutive semesters of senior students. In this process, the project has undergone changes because of observations and results. The capstone project promotes active learning since the student must seek answers to real problems outside the classroom, which requires using critical thinking, applying knowledge acquired during the career, and making decisions to find effective solutions.

4.1 Bridging theory and practice

The field of construction management faces challenges in integrating theory with practice. Simulating construction processes in educational settings is difficult, and even more so is carrying out real projects due to the scarcity of field trips and site visits. These limitations are partly due to the size of student groups and safety concerns at construction sites. An innovative approach to bridging this gap between theory and practice is through Capstone Projects using BIM. Here, deliverables such as plans, specifications, scheduling, and budgets provide an opportunity to link theory with the reality of construction.

Integrating BIM methodology into these projects allows students to model buildings, identify properties of elements, and gain a better understanding of project complexity. Additionally, BIM tools streamline the procurement of quantities for project development. The inclusion of sustainability elements is facilitated by intuitive applications like EDGE Green Building Certification application, which provide information without the need for complex design programs.

4.2 Strengths, weaknesses, and areas of improvement

The Capstone Project has allowed us to identify strengths and weaknesses in our undergraduate students. In the technical component, it has served to confirm that UIS Civil Engineering students have a strong foundation in Structural design, while weaknesses have been found in other areas of the program. This has led to proposing curricular reforms for the program and revising study plans. Additionally, areas for improvement have been identified in soft skills such as oral and written communication, as well as other aspects of collaborative work.

The most important lessons learned in formulating the Capstone project are presented below:

Team formation: Students autonomously form teams based on preferences, with a designated team leader responsible for deliverables. Team based on preferences have better performance than teams assigned by instructors.

Partial Submissions: Each semester, students are required to make three submissions, comprising two partial submissions and one final submission. This structure fosters continuous progress and allows for timely feedback. Initial Capstone Projects lacked partial submissions, resulting in unforeseen final submission quality. Partial submissions facilitate corrections and establish timeframes for progress.

Evidence of Team Collaboration: To cultivate teamwork skills, evidence of collaborative work is mandated. Students are instructed in utilizing platforms such as Trello or Task App for Microsoft Teams. An example of the evidence of team collaboration using Trello is displayed in Figure (Left).

Display of Work Schedule: Despite emphasizing project execution planning, student groups often exhibit reactive task completion as deadlines loom. Requiring documentation of the work schedule ensures an understanding of the time required for project completion. Figure 1 (Right) shows an example of work schedule for project completion using Microsoft Project.

Figure 1. Left: Team collaboration using Trello. Right: Work schedule

Clarity in Submission Requirements: Clear and precise statements are essential to ensure comprehensive delivery of required information, facilitating review and grading. Table 2 shows an example of the requirements for the first submission requirements of the capstone project.

Table 2. Capstone project- Submission requirements.

Item		Description	Percentage
Item 01	WBS	A schematic WBS [in Project or other similar software]	40%
		Propose at least three levels of the WBS	
		The breakdown must be done considering what was covered in class	
		The last proposed level should allow tracking of work progress [work packages]	
		Define the dictionary only for the last level of breakdown [work package] according to what was seen in class	
Item 02	3D Model	Model created in BIM Buildings with earthworks movements	30%
		Model created in BIM Buildings with the structural system	
		Model created in BIM Buildings with the architectural system	
Item 03	Drawings	Site plan	20%
		Architectural plan	
		Structural plan	
Item 04	Report	A written report to support the assumptions, considerations, and calculations made.	10%

Oral Presentations: Oral presentations enhance communication skills and provide opportunities for clarifying points not covered in written documents. Both slide and poster presentations serve distinct purposes. Figure 2 (Left) shows an image of a team during their presentation.

Utilization of Templates and Examples: Templates offer students guidance on presenting specific information, enhancing submission quality. The templates are given to students during the semester, and an example of a template is shown in Figure 2 (Right).

Figure 2. Left: Oral presentations. Right: Template for drawings

5 Conclusion

In conclusion, active learning methodologies, particularly through capstone projects, serve as a bridge between theoretical concepts and practical applications in construction engineering and management education. These projects, supported by using active learning strategies and methodologies like Building Information Modelling (BIM) and sustainability features, offer students hands-on experiences to apply theoretical knowledge to real-world scenarios. Despite the evident benefits, implementing active learning approaches in the curriculum can present challenges, including balancing theoretical and practical components, managing increased professor workload, and coordinating logistics for project implementation. However, addressing these challenges is crucial for ensuring the effectiveness of active learning initiatives and preparing students adequately for the dynamic demands of the construction industry. Through continuous assessment and curriculum reforms, educational institutions can strive towards providing students with comprehensive preparation and fostering their success in the field of construction engineering and management. By leveraging active learning strategies and integrating emerging technologies, educational institutions can create transformative learning experiences that equip students with the necessary skills and competencies for successful careers in construction engineering and management.

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